

InvestCEC

Plan for the Dissemination and Exploitation Including Communication Activities

Greenovate! Europe

Funded by
the European Union

Project information

Project name	InvestCEC
Full project name	Supporting the transition towards circular economy in European cities and regions: Development of a replicable model for local circular economy projects
Grant number	101082131
Project coordinator	Yoram Bar Zeev, Enspire Science Ltd. ybz@enspire-science.com
Project duration	01/11/2022 – 31/10/2025

Document information

Deliverable name and number	D4.4 - Plan for the Dissemination and Exploitation Including Communication Activities- Final version
Due date	30/09/2025
Actual submission date	27/10/2025
Contributing partners	Greenovate! Europe, Enspire Science Ltd., Stadtwerke Klagenfurt, Venionaire Capital, CARTIF, Gate2Growth
Deliverable type	
R	X
DEM	
DEC	
OTHER	
Dissemination level	
PU	X
SEN	

Version	Date	Author	Comments
1.0	9/09/2025	Giorgio Alessandro (G!E)	First Version
2.0	15/09/2025	Andrea Motola (Enspire) and Abi Glaser (Enspire)	Comments from coordinator
3.0	16/09/2025	Giorgio Alessandro (G!E)	Second version
4.0	23/09/2025	Andrea Motola (Enspire), Yoram Bar-Zeev (Enspire), Jorge Calvo Presa (CARTIF), Uffe Bundgaard Jørgensen (G2G), Paul Marian Stern, (Venionaire Capital), Yannick Lingers (Stadtwerke Klagenfurt)	Comments from partners
5.0	29/09/2025	Andrea Motola (Enspire), Yoram Bar-Zeev (Enspire)	Review
6.0	30/09/2025	Giorgio Alessandro (G!E)	Final version

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1. Introduction

1.1. About the Plan for Dissemination and Exploitation Including Communication Activities

This document focuses on the following reference tasks: **T4.1 - T4.2 – Communication Activities, T4.3 – Dissemination Activities, and T4.4 – Synergies with Relevant Initiatives and Projects**. It provides an updated version of the plan for dissemination, communication and exploitation of project results reported in D4.1 as well as any potential future activities. The Plan for Dissemination and Exploitation including Communication Activities is based on the activities described in the Dissemination and Communication Impact. The report is organized into four chapters, detailing the activities carried out under each task, an overview of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) monitoring as of September 2025, and the final learnings and conclusions.

2. Communication Activities

2.1. Project Branding

The first stage in the project communication activities was the branding of the project. To this end, Greenovate! Europe developed:

- *A project logo with alternate versions*
- *Branded document templates in Microsoft Word and PowerPoint*
- *A brand book including **InvestCEC** colours and fonts*
- *A roll up banner for use at events and meetings*

These materials were shared with partners and used for all **InvestCEC** communications during physical events and consortium meetings. By equipping partners with these assets, the project fostered unified representation at events and meetings, contributing to stronger stakeholder engagement and improved visibility of the InvestCEC project and public awareness regarding circular economy initiatives.

2.2. Website

The website has been one of the main communication channels and repository of information for the project. This has been developed by Greenovate! Europe and is hosted on the domain: <https://investcec.eu/>. From Month 1 of the project, a landing page was created, explaining the project concept and inviting users to sign up to the newsletter. The project website will be available until **October 2030**.

As of August 2025, the website has received **13 K visits**. The top three most visited pages are **the homepage** (4,1k), the **About** (805), and **News & Events** (760). As for the **geographical origin** of active users, the project has reached the highest number of users in the United States, Austria, Israel, United Kingdom and Spain, Belgium and China.

The website includes the following sections:

- **Home page** highlighting key information and partners
- **About the project page** summarising the project concept and objectives (**also available in German**)
- **Replication page** compiling resources, guides, funding opportunities, and a contact form (case-specific lab) for potential replicators of the **InvestCEC** solution (**also available in German**)
- **Marketplace** which features companies driving sustainable change and are aligned with InvestCEC mission (**also available in German**)
- **News & Events page** where the latest project news are added, and where relevant events are showcased
- **Resources page** where all public deliverables, communication materials, press releases, and replication materials deriving from the project are being published

- **Contact** page, including details for the project coordinator and communication responsible

One of the main website updates in Reporting Period 2 was the development of the InvestCEC **Marketplace** page. It features companies selected through the call for entrepreneurs and provides information about their focus area, stage, location, and year of foundation. The marketplace is also open to external companies that are aligned with the InvestCEC vision. To increase its reach and impact, particularly in Austria and Germany, the page was translated into German. The promotion via partner STW-AG also was encouraged by G!E and Enspire.

Additionally, the Marketplace was shared with the **CCRI team (February 2025) as a success story** to be promoted across relevant European networks and via **Hubs4Circularity Discussion Forum** (via Enspire team in July 2025). InvestCEC will continue to promote the **Marketplace** to expand its content and visibility, aiming to include an increasing number of innovative companies. The promotion will involve **social media campaigns and personal invitations** to entrepreneurs from the second Call for entrepreneurs.

Topic: Explore the InvestCEC Circular Economy Marketplace

Publisher: [Andrea Motola](#) Published on: 13/07/2025 08:30

Are you looking to showcase your circular economy solution or discover scalable innovations? The InvestCEC Marketplace is now live, serving as a dedicated online platform for promoting circular technologies and accelerating their uptake across Europe. The Marketplace connects **entrepreneurs, cities/regions, and investors** across Europe. It showcases a growing catalogue of circular products and services— all with clear, actionable info for decision-makers.

 Visit the Marketplace: <https://investcec.eu/marketplace/>

Figure 1 - Marketplace promotion

Figure 2 – InvestCEC website active users by country

2.3. Project Videos

Greenovate! Europe has developed and promoted **three videos** for the InvestCEC project. The development and promotion of these videos significantly contributed to raising awareness and enhancing engagement with both general and specialized audiences. By addressing different facets of the InvestCEC project—from its overarching goals to specific stakeholder perspectives—these videos helped convey complex information in an accessible and relatable format. These materials have been published on the project website and social media to maximise visibility and impact:

1. [InvestCEC - Supporting the transition toward circular economy in cities and regions](#)
2. [The InvestCEC Fund – Interview with Berthold Baurek-Karlic](#)
3. [Interview with Stadtwerke Klagenfurt and Autonome Energiesysteme](#)

Together, these videos have received a total of **414 views** on YouTube. This multimedia approach supported broader visibility, reinforced key project messages, and laid the groundwork for continued digital engagement as InvestCEC progresses. The InvestCEC introductory video has also been promoted in external events, including the **Circular Economy Day in Klagenfurt** on April 18th 2024 where it reached highly relevant audiences such as municipal **representatives** and **investors**. The video will also be showcased at the **Stadtwerke Day** (targeting approximately 1000 people) and the **InvestCEC Final Event** (50 participants onsite).

2.4. Print Materials

Printed materials have been produced during the project and distributed during fairs and conferences indicated in Table 1. These materials aim to communicate project objectives, practical insights, and results. These include:

- The **InvestCEC flyer** (in [English](#) and [German](#))
- Five **InvestCEC factsheets** presenting project results and guides.
 - InvestCEC Factsheet 1: **Circular Investment in Cities & Regions**
 - InvestCEC Factsheet 2: **Risk Factors in Circular Economy investments**
 - InvestCEC Factsheet 3: **Circular Economy Solution Areas for Urban/Regional Settings**
 - InvestCEC Factsheet 4: **What do Investors look for in companies**
 - InvestCEC Factsheet 5: **Kalundborg symbiosys – A world leading Circular Economy model**

Figure 3 - InvestCEC factsheet examples

2 FACTSHEET

Risk Factors in Circular Economy Investments

The InvestCEC project is developing a scalable model for implementing circular economy projects in European cities and regions by partnering circular entrepreneurs with public municipalities seeking circular services. **The pilot programme is being tested in Klagenfurt, Austria**

The shift to a circular economy is not only about recycling old products, it is about redefining how businesses create value. For investors looking to tap into this growing movement, there are two key strategies:

DIRECT CIRCULARITY

Businesses that physically close material loops (regeneration, reuse, waste-to-resource).

- Clear environmental impact
- Strong alignment with circular goals
- Dependence on volatile supply chains
- Market demand fluctuations
- Capital-intensive and regulated
- Waste-to-energy plants
- Electronics/textile remanufacturing
- Biodegradable material startups

ENABLING CIRCULARITY

Businesses that provide tools, tech, or services that support circular models.

- Lower operational risk
- High scalability across sectors
- Resilient to supply chain disruptions
- Future-proof technology
- Indirect impact on material flows
- Market uptake of tech may vary
- Smart waste platforms (e.g., Wastebox)
- AI-driven logistics
- Blockchain for material traceability

KEY TAKEAWAYS
What strategies are better for investing into the circular economy?

Drive visible, hands-on change, they carry higher operational risk.

Offer broader, more resilient, and often lower-risk opportunities, particularly appealing to investors seeking long-term scalability and cross-sector relevance.

To showcase profitability and long-term value creation and to build confidence, circular businesses must highlight their financial resilience, cost savings, and competitive advantages.

Investments in resource efficiency, waste reduction, and sustainable design often lead to lower production costs, stronger brand positioning, and higher long-term returns.

LEARN MORE IN THE INVESTCEC GUIDE: INVESTING IN THE CIRCULAR ECONOMY

3 FACTSHEET

What Do Investors Look For in Companies?

Investors conducting due diligence on startups focus on the business's financial health, market opportunity, scalability, and ability to deliver measurable environmental and social impact. Preparing for this scrutiny is critical to building trust and securing funding.

Impact investors are particularly drawn to startups that align with circular economy principles and can show strong potential for:

- Impact
- Growth
- Profitability

PRIORITY AREAS FOR INVESTORS INCLUDE

- Digital resource tracking
- Regenerative materials
- Extending product lifespans
- Turning waste into value
- Adopting innovative business models

Checklist

FINANCIAL HEALTH AND KPIS

- Clear revenue, expenses, profit margins, and cash flow
- Historical financial statements (2-3 years) and 3-5 year projections
- Key metrics: CAC, LTV, Burn Rate, Churn Rate, Revenue Growth

TRACTION AND TEAM

- Proof of product-market fit and demand
- Growth metrics: revenue trends, customer acquisition, retention
- Experience level of the management team, board and advisors
- Strong partnerships or pilot projects

MARKET OPPORTUNITY AND COMPETITIVE EDGE

- Market size: TAM, SAM, SOM
- Unique technology, IP or partnerships
- Plans to manage market and regulatory risks

PRODUCT AND TECHNOLOGY VALIDATION

- Product milestones and roadmap
- Proof of innovation: patents, validations, deployments

LEGAL AND REGULATORY COMPLIANCE

- Up-to-date corporate and Intellectual Property documents
- Compliance with environmental and data privacy laws
- Reliable contracts and truthful marketing

LEARN MORE IN THE CIRCULAR ECONOMY FUNDRAISING HANDBOOK

4 FACTSHEET

Circular Economy Solution Areas For Urban/Regional Settings

The InvestCEC project is developing a scalable model for implementing circular economy projects in European cities and regions by partnering circular entrepreneurs with public municipalities seeking circular services. **The pilot programme is being tested in Klagenfurt, Austria**

Governance and public policies are key to driving the circular economy in cities and regions. They provide the frameworks, incentives, and coordination needed to overcome barriers and scale circular initiatives.

The Circular Economy Action Plan serves as the main guidance document to drive circularity across cities and regions across Europe.

OUTLINED SOLUTIONS AT URBAN AND REGIONAL LEVEL TO PROMOTE CIRCULARITY PRACTICES

Embrace technological innovation by investing in local R&D for circular solutions

Provide regulatory harmonisation to align local, regional, and national policies

Support education and awareness campaigns to align local, regional, and national policies

Provide financial incentives to develop funding tools and support mechanisms

IDENTIFIED EXAMPLES OF EFFECTIVE POLICY MEASURES

Development of local circular economy strategies

Implementation of circular public procurement systems

Promotion of multi-stakeholder collaboration (business, academia, citizens)

Creation of circular innovation hubs for startups and SMEs

Target-setting and tracking measurable circular goals

LEARN MORE IN THE CIRCULAR ECONOMY SOLUTION AREAS FOR URBAN/REGIONAL SETTINGS REPORT

5 FACTSHEET

Kalundborg Symbiosis: A World-Leading Circular Economy Model

Since 1972 in the city of Kalundborg, Denmark, the world's first industrial symbiosis with a circular approach to production was developed. It brings together 17 public and private organisations, to collaborate and exchange energy, water, and material resources.

The main principle is simple yet extremely effective: one company's by-product becomes another's input, reducing environmental impact while improving competitiveness.

HOW DOES IT WORK?

- Public and private companies are physically connected.
- They share surplus steam, heat, water, and materials.
- The model is based on trust, cooperation, and long-term vision.

IMPACTS AND BENEFITS

Economic

- Lower production costs
- Business growth
- Positive ROI for all partners

Environmental

- Fewer CO₂ emissions
- Waste reduction
- Efficient use of natural resources

Social

- Local job creation
- Community resilience
- Strong local partnerships

Kalundborg Symbiosis proves that the circular economy works, reducing waste, cutting emissions, and boosting Denmark's green leadership.

It supports the national goal **70% REDUCTION**

Driven by strong public-private collaboration, shared infrastructure, smart energy systems, and aligned incentives, it shows how trust and innovation can scale circular solutions. **Kalundborg is a real-world example of how the circular economy thrives as a model to replicate across cities and regions across Europe.**

LEARN MORE THE KALUNDBORG SYMBIOSIS IN THE CIRCULAR ECONOMY SOLUTION AREAS FOR URBAN/REGIONAL SETTINGS REPORT

2.5. Social Media

The project has regularly promoted **project activities, related news, articles, videos, and updates on the InvestCEC social media channels**, with the [project LinkedIn page](#) as the primary social media channel. During Reporting Period 2 (RP2), the consortium made the strategic decision to discontinue its presence on Platform X in order to concentrate communication efforts on LinkedIn and enhance the channel's overall impact. Given InvestCEC's focus on engaging entrepreneurs and investors, LinkedIn was identified as the most suitable platform for reaching these target audiences effectively. As of September 2025, the InvestCEC LinkedIn page has grown to **496 followers** and continues to serve as a key tool for stakeholder engagement and outreach.

The InvestCEC LinkedIn channel has also functioned as the main hub for the promotion of the **discussion forum**, which aimed to stimulate discussions among interested stakeholders regarding circular Investments. The forum has engaged users, including **CCRI Projects (BioBoost) and entrepreneurs** (e.g. Comtek Network Systems). To amplify our impact and outreach, the discussion forum has been established on the InvestCEC [LinkedIn page](#) and connected to the InvestCEC website.

Some other examples of the campaigns on the InvestCEC LinkedIn page are available below:

- [Series of videos on the InvestCEC fund](#)
- [Meet the InvestCEC selected companies](#)
- [InvestCEC series of webinars](#)
- [Meet the InvestCEC/RESOURCE Policy Workshop speakers](#)
- [Webinars video wrap-up](#)

Figure 4 - Example: InvestCEC discussion forum

2.6. Newsletter

The InvestCEC project has issued **6 newsletters**, sent to 231 subscribers (as of September 2025) that signed up to receive the newsletter via a form on the **project website and on LinkedIn**. To increase the number of subscribers the InvestCEC project will launch a wide **dissemination campaign** of the last issue of the newsletter, which will be published in September 2025 and will include a wrap-up of the main achievements of the project. The newsletter will **leverage the partners' wide network** of followers on LinkedIn, such as Venionaire (4k followers), CARTIF (13k followers), Greenovate! Europe (3,2k followers).

The last newsletter will also include a link to register for the InvestCEC final event. All the newsletter issues are available at the links below:

- [September 2023](#)
- [December 2023](#)
- [March 2024](#)
- [September 2024](#)
- [December 2024](#)
- [April 2025](#)
- [September 2025](#)

2.7. Content creation and press releases

2.7.1. ARTICLES AND INTERVIEWS

Throughout the project, **Greenovate! Europe** has coordinated the creation of content such as project **news, articles, and interviews for dissemination on the project website and social media**, which are available on the [News & Events website page](#). **Interviews** with partners and entrepreneurs were also conducted and published on the website to increase public awareness about the project. Furthermore, the project has also been featured in presentations delivered by partners during events, thus reaching specialised audiences more effectively. For example, a non-exhaustive list of content created by InvestCEC partners (in English and in German) is presented below:

- [Call for Entrepreneurs – present your circular economy solution to decision makers](#)
- [InvestCEC at the EU Green Week 2025](#)
- [InvestCEC interview with G2G](#)
- [InvestCEC at the Cirplex Summit 2025](#)
- [Policy Workshop – Addressing Current Barriers to Circular Investment: Policy Approaches for Success](#)
- [Digital Solutions for Circular Economy: Leveraging Technology in Urban Settings](#)

- [Let's Talk about Tech Podcast: the Power of Social Impact in Business \(InvestCEC mentioned by Venionaire Capital\)](#)
- [Circular Economy Day 2024: Startschuss für 20 Millionen InvestCEC-Fonds](#)
- [Press release: Circular Economy Kreislaufwirtschaft in Millionenhole](#)
- [Innovation entsteht dort, wo der Wille dafür da ist“: Venionaire Capital unterstützt Klagenfurter Startup-Initiativen](#)
- [Addressing Current Barriers to Circular Investment: Policy approaches for success](#)
- [The InvestCEC Project hold its 3rd follow-up meeting at CARTIF to advance the development and implementation of a replicable model for the circular economy in the EU](#)

2.7.2. PROMOTION OF THE FUND

Special attention has been given to the promotion of the fund in order to reach a high number of relevant investors. In particular, **Venionaire Capital leveraged its website (over ten thousands of users), LinkedIn (over 4k followers), and email newsletter (over ten thousands of subscribers) to promote the InvestCEC Project and the Fund project.** Venionaire Capital has reached out to over **450 potential investors across Europe** to promote the fund project. Venionaire Capital is leveraging outreach via partner and cluster alliances, including Invest Klagenfurt, Green Tech Valley, BABEG, PDIE Group, Universe Partners, Una Terra and others. Furthermore, the fund project is being actively promoted by Venionaire Capital at **events and public presentations**, such as: CIRPLEX, Start(up) Friday Pörschach, World Venture Forum, Climate Week NYC, and others.

2.7.3. CALL FOR ENTREPRENEURS

Particular effort has been made by the project in disseminating **press releases of the two calls for entrepreneurs** via various channels, including their publication in **Austrian, Swiss, and German media**. This targeted approach aimed to attract entrepreneurs from Austria and neighbouring German speaking countries, thereby maximising engagement with the city of Klagenfurt.

Some **examples** are available below:

- [Press release: InvestCEC Second Call for Entrepreneurs](#)
- [Super Angels Club – InvestCEC Call for Entrepreneurs](#)
- [Presse Portal CH](#)
- [Presse Portal DE](#)

Partners have also used their channels to actively promote the calls: **Venionaire Capital AG leveraged its website, LinkedIn, email newsletters, press releases, and outreach through partners and cluster alliances also to promote both calls for entrepreneurs; Gate2Growth** circulated information about the Call for Entrepreneurs at the “funding bazar” events at the **Danish Technology University Science park.**

The “call for entrepreneurs” was also disseminated to a wide audience via various types of on-line and social media, and with direct contact to organisations like the European Enterprise Network and

other similar organisations working with European entrepreneurs and SMEs. Furthermore, the call for entrepreneurs was promoted via an e-mail campaign by Greenovate and Enspire to **Horizon Europe EIC National Contact Points in all Member States**, which shared the call for entrepreneurs with their networks and through their social media channels.

Some examples of social **media post** on the [InvestCEC LinkedIn](#) to raise awareness about the call for entrepreneurs are available below:

- [Example 1 \(5 February, 2025\)](#)
- [Example 2 \(20 December, 2024\)](#)
- [Example 3 \(17 December, 2024\)](#)

In total, **the call for entrepreneurs** received a total of **59 applications** (16 in Call for Entrepreneurs 1, and 43 applications in Call for Entrepreneurs 2) with a diverse geographical and technological scope.

Figure 5 - CFE call for entrepreneurs applications grouped on focus area

3. Dissemination Activities

3.1. Activities

Greenovate! Europe organised several dissemination activities to present project activities and intermediate results in cooperation with project partners and CCRI projects and stakeholders, including dissemination of project guides, event organisation, and presentation of project results.

3.1.1. PUBLICATION OF PROJECT GUIDES

Greenovate! Europe has published all the guides prepared by partners (VENCAP, G2G, STW-Ag and CARTIF) and approved deliverables on the InvestCEC [Zenodo Community](#) and project website. These materials are open to the public and available for downloading, to ensure long-term availability and findability. The InvestCEC partners have produced a **series of guidebooks** and materials to provide interested users with valuable resources on circular economy transition in urban settings/circular economy investments and support national and European replication of the lessons learnt within the project.

- [Circular Economy Solution Areas for Urban/Regional Settings](#)
- [InvestCEC Guide for Investors: Inve@sting in the Circular Economy](#)
- [Circular Economy Fundraising Guidebook](#)
- [Guidelines on Circular Economy Transition](#)
- [Templates for local and regional authorities/entrepreneurs](#)
- [Replication Plan](#)
- [Monitoring Investment Opportunities](#)

Furthemore, Greenovate! Europe has put particular particular effort into organising impactful online events with a broad variety of speakers. A summary of events organized by Greenovate! Europe is presented in the table below.

Table 1 - Dissemination Activities

Title	Type	CCRI Stakeholders involved	Date	Number of participants
Empowering Entrepreneurs for Investment Success	Thematic webinar	DEFINITE-CCRI	11 April 2024	34
Breaking Down Financial Barriers	Thematic webinar	DECISO	30 April 2024	39

Financing the Circular Future	Thematic webinar	BioBoost	26 November 2024	82
Fostering Replication and Policy Change	Thematic webinar	HOOP and CircularInvest	5 December 2024	30
Addressing Current Barriers to Circular Investment	Policy Workshop	RESOURCE	3 April 2025	65

3.2. InvestCEC Final Event

The InvestCEC has officially scheduled its final event (online and onsite), which will take place in Brussels at the **European Parliament on Tuesday, October 14th, 2025** from 14:30 to 16:30. This high-level event will showcase the project main outcomes, explore opportunities for replication, and foster dialogue between local and EU policymakers, investors, and circular companies. A particular focus will be placed on the the role of local/EU policies to foster green public procurement and public-private partnerships. The agenda will include:

- The presentation of InvestCEC methodology and reflection on lessons learnt and next steps
- An insightful panel session with Member of the European Parliament **Sandro Gozi**, **René Cerne** (Klagenfurt City Council Member), a circular entrepreneur (**Kathrina Rieger**, Austria Regional Manager, Concular), and **Maya Poncelet** (Head of Partnerships, Una Terra Growth Fund)

The event has also already been promoted on the [InvestCEC website](#) and targets an audience of at least **200 participants** including onsite and online participants. Additionally, targeted promotion of the event via personal invitations to relevant stakeholders (EU Institutions, NGOs and Civil Society, Investors, etc.) has started in August 2025. The event will be also shared via the CCRI Intranet and newsletter, the [European Circular Economy Stakeholder Platform](#) and Hubs for Circularity Platform to maximise engagement with relevant target audiences.

3.3. Participation in External events

As of August 2025, the InvestCEC partners participated in more than 20 external events onsite to network with relevant stakeholders and present project main achievements.

Table 2 - External events attended by InvestCEC partners

Event	Stakeholders involved	Date
World Venture Forum 2023, Austria	All partners	July 2023

Climate Week NYC 2024 / Clinton Global Initiative Annual Meeting / The Future of Climate Summit Vol. II Recap	Venionaire Capital	19-24 September 2024
ECOMONDO Fair in Rimini	G2G, Enspire	November 2023
1 st CCRI General Conference	G!E, Materalia	8 November 2023
11th Public Utility Day	Stadtwerke Klagenfurt	23 November 2023
European Week of Regions and Cities	Greenovate! Europe	7-10 October 2024
Alpen Adria Businessclubs Klagenfurt	Venionaire Capital	17 September 2024
World Circular Economy Forum 2024	Greenovate! Europe	15-16 April 2024
EU Green Week 2024	Greenovate! Europe	29-30 May 2024
World Venture Forum 2024, Austria	Venionaire Capital	1-6 July 2024
DECISO Project Conference 2024, Belgium	Greenovate! Europe	9 October 2024
3 rd CCRI Coordination and Support Workshop, Belgium	Venionaire Capital	13 November 2024
CCRI Circular Investing – Pitching Investment Opportunities	Greenovate! Europe	20 March 2025
CIRPLEX Summit, Klagenfurt, Austria	Greenovate! Europe, Venionaire Capital, and Stadtwerke Klagenfurt	13-15 May 2025
The Venture Mindset	Venionaire Capital	29 April 2025
Green Tech seePORT Pörtlach	Venionaire Capital	23 May 2025
EU Green Week, Belgium	Greenovate! Europe and Enspire	3-5 June 2025
4 th CCRI Coordination and Support Workshop	Greenovate! Europe	6 June
World Venture Forum 2025 (Impact Alm), Austria	Venionaire Capital	30 June – 6 July 2025
Climate Week NYC 2025/ Clinton Global Initiative Annual Meeting	Venionaire Capital	20-25 September 2025
Stadtwerke Klagenfurt Day	Stadtwerke Klagenfurt	27 September 2025

4. Synergies with Relevant Initiatives and Projects

InvestCEC has worked closely with other CCRI projects under the same call. In November 2023, an initial collaboration workshop was organized by GIE with all **6 fellow CCRI-PDA projects (HOOP, Circular Invest, DEFINITE-CCRI, Resource, BioBoost and DECISO)** to introduce the projects and explore networking opportunities among each other, particularly in communication and dissemination activities. The InvestCEC newsletter and social media channels were used as tools to actively feature news and updates from key collaborators, allowing for ongoing engagement and cross-dissemination. Partners are also active within the CCRI community, following the thematic working groups and attending the General Conference.

4.1. InvestCEC webinars with CCRI projects

As part of InvestCEC clustering activities, CCRI project representatives have been invited to participate as attendees/speakers in webinars organized by InvestCEC on topics of common interest. A list of events where CCRI projects contributed is presented below (a detailed breakdown is presented in Table 1):

- InvestCEC Webinar: **Empowering Entrepreneurs for Investment Success** – with Tommaso Buso (DEFINITE – CCRI)
- InvestCEC Webinar: **Breaking Down Financial Barriers** with DECISO Project
- InvestCEC Webinar: **Financing the Circular Future** – with Emma Pipo Olle (BioBoost Project)
- InvestCEC Webinar **Fostering Replication and Policy Change** – with Elisa Gambuzzi (HOOP Project) and Lorenzo Valeriani (CircularInvest)

4.2. InvestCEC/RESOURCE policy workshop

InvestCEC also co-organized the policy workshop **Addressing Current Barriers to Circular Investment – Policy Approaches for Success** with the CCRI project RESOURCE. The workshop successfully attracted **65 participants**, who actively participated in the interactive sessions. The sessions proposed several activities, such as rating policy recommendations,

Figure 6 – InvestCEC/RESOURCE Policy Workshop

defining main obstacles to investment in circular businesses, and proposing policies to overcome these obstacles.

The workshop was opened by a keynote speech by **Lucie Blondel**, Policy Officer at DG Research and Innovation and CCRI Coordinator. The event also featured a **distinguished panel of experts, including Katarzyna Balucka-Debska** (Climate KIC), **Jonas Byström** (European Investment Bank), **Marco Musso** (European Environmental Bureau), and **Chema Pina Sánchez-Mariscal** (Aptki Global Partners and Fork Capital). The panel discussion was moderated by **Uffe Bundgaard-Jorgensen**, CEO and Founder of Gate2Growth, member of the InvestCEC project.

Participants actively engaged through polls during the workshop (moderated by Hélène Dworak, Public Policy Expert at G.A.C. Group, member of RESOURCE project) providing valuable insights into policy priorities and investment barriers. These insights helped refine policy recommendations for both projects and resulted in the production of a **joint policy brief** to be published in **September/October 2025**, which will amplify the policy outreach of the two projects.

The policy brief has been finalised and will be published on the InvestCECE and RESOURCE websites once approved by the Project Officer.

4.3. Collaboration with BioBoost

To maximise synergies with other CCRI projects, InvestCEC has also initiated collaboration with the [BioBoost project](#). This has resulted in the identification of common challenges for investments in circular companies, particularly concerning fragmented regulatory frameworks and strict procurement processes. Several recommendations from InvestCEC closely align with those proposed in the BioBoost policy brief. For example, consistent with our own findings, BioBoost and InvestCEC highlight legal and regulatory barriers, as well as the lack of financial incentives, as significant obstacles:

- **EU Policy Recommendation No. 1** – Addressing regulatory and legal barriers across Member States requires harmonizing standards and criteria at the EU level within the bioeconomy sector.
- **Local/Regional Policy Recommendation No. 3** – To support investors and project developers in the bioeconomy sector in mitigating high market risks, specific measures and instruments should be implemented to reduce uncertainty, thereby promoting investment in the sector.

This shared understanding underscores the importance of collaborative efforts, as many of the barriers experienced in Klagenfurt are also prevalent elsewhere.

5. Exploitation

5.1. Methodology used

As described in **D4.2 – Plan for Dissemination and Exploitation including Communication Activities**, the project exploitation is nominally led by Greenovate! Europe within Task 3.4, however it is the responsibility of all partners. **IP management** is being overseen by Enspire Science within WP1 and is described in more detail in section 5.3.

Exploitation is also closely linked to Replication which is being led by VENCAP in WP3, after Materialia's departure. The project **Replication Plan was outlined in D3.1**.

GIE has overseen a series of Exploitation related activities to help ensure the above objectives are achieved: The partners have started from the beginning of the project to work on exploitation. Several steps were carried out throughout the project. The detailed methodology and timeline is described in Table 7.

Table 3: Exploitation activities

Activity Timeline Description		
Identification of key project results	M4	A first mapping of key project results has been carried out and confirmed by all partners. This is included in section 3.
Drafting of the project Dissemination and Exploitation plan – initial version	M6	The current report, which aims to elaborate the objectives and actions related to exploitation and dissemination.
Exploitation meetings	M26	Reflection on results to be exploited during the project
Clarification of Results list	M30	Discussion and update of KER
Dissemination and Exploitation Plan	M35	Final exploitation plan
Open Access Publishing	M1- M36	All public outcomes of the project have been published in open access channels and repositories (Zenodo) according to the strategy explained in section 6.5.

5.2. Exploitation strategies identified and Key Exploitable Results

Partners have analysed the project learnings within their organisations to determine how they will apply specific results beyond the project's lifetime. In the table below, each KER is described based on the KER description, project result used, the proposed exploitation action, etc.

A summary table is presented below.

Table 4 – Project KERs

KER name	Status	Short description
InvestCEC model for circular economy projects	Autumn 25	The final version of InvestCEC model for circular economy projects describing its 4 stages, including all practices, methods, tools and materials.
InvestCEC Investment Programme	October 25	The InvestCEC Investment Programme provides guidelines for establishing a dedicated €20M Circular Economy Venture Capital Fund (AIF) and an investor network enabling co-investment and deal sharing. It defines fund facts, investment focus areas, evaluation criteria, and templates for fund setup. The programme ensures that investments are aligned with circular economy principles, supporting startups and SMEs across Greentech, Renewable Energy, Smart Logistics, Sharing Economy, Waste Management, and other CE-related sectors.
InvestCEC Policy Recommendations	Available	The Final Policy Recommendation Brief is the end-of-project policy recommendation report, outlining InvestCEC's experience-based advice for policy makers to promote the transition towards a circular economy at the EU and city/region level. The Final Policy Recommendations updated the preliminary policy recommendations drafted in Deliverable 3.3 – Mid-term Policy Recommendation Brief.
Guide: Circular Economy Solution Areas for Urban/Regional Setting	Available	A practical guide to identifying and deploying circular economy solutions in urban and regional environments, framed within the InvestCEC project. Its aim is to facilitate the transition to more sustainable models by identifying opportunities in key sectors: waste management, energy, mobility, construction and sustainable consumption/production. The guide offers examples of European success stories (Vienna, Copenhagen, Amsterdam, Kalundborg, among others) that show how to apply circular principles to optimise resources, reduce CO ₂ emissions and improve urban resilience. It also provides a reference framework for local and regional authorities seeking to implement replicable circular economy projects, highlighting the environmental, social and economic benefits of these strategies.
InvestCEC guide for Investors: Investing in the Circular Economy	Available	The Guide for Investors provides educational material to build awareness and confidence in circular economy investments. It explains the importance of CE, highlights risks and opportunities, and introduces financial instruments, government incentives, and case studies. It distinguishes between direct and enabling circularity

		investments, outlines evaluation methods such as Life Cycle Assessment and circular economy metrics, and presents successful CE business models. The guide helps investors understand CE-specific risks, regulatory developments (EU Green Deal, CSRD, EU Taxonomy), and funding models (green bonds, impact funds, PPPs).
Circular Economy Fundraising Guidebook	Available	The Fundraising Guidebook provides circular economy startups, investors, and policymakers with practical insights and tools for financing CE solutions. It explains fundraising fundamentals, valuation methods, investor expectations, and negotiation strategies, while addressing the specific challenges and ESG implications of CE business models. It supports entrepreneurs in preparing for investment and helps investors understand risks, impact metrics, and opportunities in CE.
Monitoring Investments Opportunities	Available	Monitoring Investment Opportunities maps public and private funding sources for circular economy projects in European cities and regions. It categorises instruments such as grants, equity, mezzanine, loans, subsidies, and PPPs, and aligns them with CE solution typologies like waste-to-resource, reuse, product-as-a-service, and digital enablers. The analysis highlights barriers such as “circle interdependency,” investor unfamiliarity, and high transaction costs, while offering recommendations to improve investor readiness, blended finance, and better alignment between CE projects and funders.
Guidelines on Circular Economy Transitions	Available	The Guideline provide a roadmap for European medium-sized cities and public utilities to shift from linear to circular systems. It outlines how municipalities can define local needs, set objectives, design strategies, secure financing, and engage stakeholders to accelerate the circular transition. It highlights the specific context of medium-sized cities, such as Klagenfurt am Wörthersee, emphasizing their unique challenges and opportunities. Key chapters cover sector prioritization, stakeholder engagement, risk mitigation, financing models, and implementation tools. The document also stresses the importance of monitoring progress, setting milestones, and scaling pilots into systemic solutions.
InvestCEC strategy documet: Public Procurement	Available	The purpose of this document is to provide a short introduction to the nature of “Public Procurement” and illustrate how traditional public procurement processes and associated formalities pose potential barriers for the quick uptake of emerging circular economy solutions by the public sector. The document includes ideas for potential solutions for overcoming the identified barriers, based on discussions with entrepreneurs and representatives from public sector and regulatory bodies.
Catalogue of circular economy projects	October 2025	The catalogue of circular economy provides a list of circular solutions assessed by the InvestCEC project during the two calls for entrepreneurs. This catalogue has been published on the InvestCEC marketplace, where main info about the company such as company

	<p>stage, location, year and place of foundation are reported. The marketplace aims to connect circular economy solutions with potential partners (municipalities, investors, other companies etc.).</p>
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5.3. Management of intellectual property right

IP management in InvestCEC followed the principles and procedures outlined in the Grant Agreement (GA) and Consortium Agreement (CA). Background and potential results were monitored throughout the project within WP1, with Enspire Science responsible for ensuring that any potentially exploitable outcomes were identified and discussed in consortium meetings.

No new intellectual property was generated during the project. Nevertheless, the consortium ensured that IP-related considerations were continuously addressed, with reference to the European IP Helpdesk guidelines and, where appropriate, potential external expert advice.

Ownership principles were respected:

- Results would remain with the party that generated them.
- Jointly developed results would be jointly owned.

As no IP requiring protection or exploitation emerged, no further legal or technical actions were necessary.

5.4. Open Access Publishing

This means as much information as possible will be shared publicly, without jeopardising the intellectual property of any partner. The project has been designed in such a way that the majority of data and reports produced by the project will be public documents. Indeed many of the results, such as the replication manuals, have been designed with the express intention of being made public.

All the project guides have been shared on the **Zenodo Community, CCRI Intranet, and Multiplier platforms such as the European Circular Economy Stakeholder Platform Knowledge Hub**, making sure that these results are available for circular economy professionals. Furthermore, some identified results will be uploaded on the **Horizon Results Platform**.

6. Key Performance Indicator Monitoring

Table 5 - Key Performance Indicators

Activity	KPI	Target	August 2025
Thematic webinars	Number of webinars	4	4
	Total attendees	200	257
Final conference	Total attendees	200	N/A
International Conferences and events	Presentations	5	8
Scientific publications (later named professional articles)	Number of articles	2	2
Project Website	Visits	30,000	13,000
Video	Views	2,000	6900 ¹
Media	Number of media hits	20	58
Newsletter	Number of subscribers	400	241
Networking	Number of projects engaged	5	6
	Number of joint events	2	5

¹ This is a compilation of views from the different videos, including the Circular Economy Day in Klagenfurt video by VENCAP.

Conclusion

The Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation Plan describes our strategy for engaging actively in communication and dissemination and exploitation activities in order to maximise the opportunities for InvestCEC results to be used and exploited at European level after the project's end. The Plan is a living document developed by Greenovate! Europe in collaboration with all partners. In addition, this last update developed in M35 reports the activities implemented throughout the project. In addition, it includes an update of the Key Exploitable Results. The document makes reference to the activities carried out during the second half of the project in terms of communications, such as interviews, press releases, material development, and participation in external events where the InvestCEC partners represented the project.